

Modeling the Impact of Void Distribution on Mechanical Properties of Short Fiber Recycled CFRTP Integration of Experimental Analysis and Finite Element Analysis

Aug 4, 2025

Takumi Morishima, Yi Wan, Jun Takahashi

morishima-takumi@cfrtp.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

The University of Tokyo

Background

Needs for recycling

[1]-[3]

[1] Modern Plastics Global, "Forecast for Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics Market Assures Growth," 2020., [2] World Energy Trade, "The Wind Industry Calls for a Ban in EUROPE on the Dumping of Wind Turbine Blades," 2021., [3] AMS Composites, "Carbon Fibre, the Environment and the Future of Recycling," 2019.

Degradation of mechanical property in recycling process

UD=Uni-directional, SMC=Sheet Mold Compound, NWF=Non-woven fabric, CPT=Carbon Paper Thermoplastics

Degradation of mechanical property in recycling process

UD=Uni-directional, SMC=Sheet Mold Compound, NWF=Non-woven fabric, CPT=Carbon Paper Thermoplastics

Deconsolidation of CPT

2mm [4]

[4] Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites, "Deconsolidation behavior of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics," 2014.

Conventional lattice void meshing

[5] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [6] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [7] Journal of Glaciology, "Stochastic reconstruction of the microstructure of equilibrium form snow and computation of effective elastic properties," 2010.

Conventional lattice void meshing

1. Image-based Conforming Mesh

- ✓ High quality
- ✓ High cost

⁽³⁾

[5]

[5] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [6] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [7] Journal of Glaciology, "Stochastic reconstruction of the microstructure of equilibrium form snow and computation of effective elastic properties," 2010.

Conventional lattice void meshing

1. Image-based Conforming Mesh

- ✓ High quality
- ✓ High cost

(3)

2. Voxel-based Mesh

- ✓ Low cost
- ✓ Rough surface

[5]

[6]

[5] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [6] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [7] Journal of Glaciology, "Stochastic reconstruction of the microstructure of equilibrium form snow and computation of effective elastic properties," 2010.

Conventional lattice void meshing

[5] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [6] Computational Mechanics, "An integrated approach for the conformal discretization of complex inclusion-based microstructures," 2019., [7] Journal of Glaciology, "Stochastic reconstruction of the microstructure of equilibrium form snow and computation of effective elastic properties," 2010.

Research objective & contribution

Objective

- Quantitatively characterize the relationship between SB ratio and void distribution patterns
- Develop a novel Python-based methodology to classify complex void geometries
- Create high-fidelity Representative Volume Element (RVE) meshes

Contribution

- Resolve the quality vs computational-cost trade-off
- Provide a robust foundation for future finite element analysis

Method

Research flow

Material preparation

$$SB_i = \frac{t_{final,i}}{t_{initial,i}} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N)$$

Material preparation

$$SB_i = \frac{t_{final,i}}{t_{initial,i}} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, N)$$

CT void modeling

Stochastic void modeling

Threshold optimization with Shannon entropy

$S = \{ \text{Cylinder, Platelet, Ellipsoid, Icosahedron} \}$

Stochastic void modeling

Threshold optimization with Shannon entropy

$$S = \{\text{Cylinder, Platelet, Ellipsoid, Icosahedron}\}$$

Objective function

$$\theta^* = \arg \max_{\theta} H(\theta)$$

where

$$\theta = (\theta_{\text{sphere}}, \theta_{\text{prolate}}, \theta_{\text{oblate}})$$

$$H(\theta) = - \sum_{i \in S} p_i(\theta) \log p_i(\theta)$$

$$p_i(\theta) = \frac{n_i(\theta)}{N}$$

under

$$1.1 \leq \theta_{\text{sphere}} \leq 1.5$$

$$1.2 \leq \theta_{\text{prolate}} \leq 1.8$$

$$1.2 \leq \theta_{\text{oblate}} \leq 1.8$$

Mesh & Discussion

RVE mesh generation

Conclusion

- Established a quantitative link between manufacturing conditions and internal structure.
- Clarified the void formation mechanism.
 - ✓ Quantified the direct link between higher springback and increased void volume, which rose to over 22%.
 - ✓ Observed that voids grow and form interconnected networks at high springback ratios.
- Developed a reliable modeling methodology.
 - ✓ Developed a Python script to automate the classification of complex voids into simple shapes for modeling.
- Generated high-fidelity analytical models.
 - ✓ Successfully generated high-fidelity Representative Volume Element (RVE) models suitable for FEA.

Future work & Acknowledgement

Future Work

- Validation of the model through comparison of FEM & experimental result

This work was supported by JST SPRING, Grant Number JPMJSP2108.

UTokyo
Green
Transformation

**Thank you and happy to
answer questions**

Takumi Morishima

morishima-takumi@cfrtp.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

The University of Tokyo

- Form vs CPT

- A little heavier
- CFRP good property
 - Shear modulus
- Recycle material
- Adhesive is problem

- <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/10996362241303054>

